

Open banking: the point of view of Italian financial advisors

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Introduction

Open banking allows third-party financial service providers to access transactions and other financial data from traditional financial institutions through an application programming interface (API). APIs ensure the secure exchange of data and instructions between parties in digital interactions, but increasing concerns arise regarding cybersecurity (Burchi et. al, 2019). The aim of this paper is to analyze the process towards the adoption of open banking services, such as the account information services, of 356 Italian financial advisors that responded to a survey we design specifically for the experiment at hand.

Methods

We consider a partial least square setting with two exogenous latent factors, the personal technology propensity and the cyber-risk aversion of financial advisors as potential drivers or deterrent to the adoption of such services. The analysis confirms our hypotheses and evidence that personal technology propensity is acting as a “boost”, whereas the cyber-risk aversion as a “brake”. This study contributes to the literature on open banking services by providing a comprehensive view of the determinants of users’ attitudes and underlines the relevance of suitable investments able to mitigate the “brake effect” of cyber-risk aversion

Results

The analysis reveals that while the standard TAM's latent constructs exhibit strong and positive causal links, the initial phase in the adoption process is notably impacted by an individual's inclination towards personal technology and their aversion to cyber risks. This finding aligns with the real-world observations of limited adoption of AIS in Italy, sparking discussions about the development of open banking under the PSD2 revision and the accompanying regulatory changes. For sure, the financial advisor acts more as a careful “change agent” than as a “blind pusher”.

References

Burchi, A., Mezzacapo, S., Musile Tanzi, P., Troiano, V., 2019. Financial Data Aggregation e Account Information Services. Questioni regolamentari e profili di business, CONSOB, Quaderni FinTech.

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